

SCHIFF'S BASES FROM SODIUM ARSANILATE

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Various aldehydes have been condensed with sodium arsanilate to furnish *Schiff's* bases, which react with sodium bisulphite to yield soluble compounds. These might prove useful in arsenic therapy.

Sodium arsanilate (Atoxyl, Soamin) is used in cases of anaemia, syphilis, elephantiasis, malaria and other protozoal diseases. It is, however, found to be somewhat toxic and its toxic effect is cumulative, often leading to complete blindness. Moreover, solution of sodium arsanilate cannot be sterilised, as it suffers decomposition.

Other isomers of atoxyl (*ortho*- and *meta*-) are inferior to atoxyl in trypanocidal activity, while the former is more toxic. The presence of a second amino group in atoxyl decreases still further the toxicity but unfortunately the activity towards parasites is also decreased, while it disappears altogether on the introduction of a third amino group. This decreasing activity is partially connected with the increasing ease with which the substances are eliminated from the body. It is therefore evident that the activity of atoxyl is associated with the presence of *para*-amino group and its toxicity has been decreased by acylation of this *para*-amino group and/or by the introduction of a hydroxyl group in the benzene nucleus. *p*-Acetylamino phenylarsonic acid is only one-third as toxic as atoxyl, but is three times therapeutically active. Aminohydroxyphenylarsonic acids are much less toxic than atoxyl and are found to manifest both trypanocidal and spirillicidal properties. The toxicity of atoxyl has also been decreased by preparing the corresponding carbamide and phenylglycine derivatives of *para*-arsanilic acid. The former is less than half as toxic as atoxyl and equally effective therapeutically, and is particularly useful in amoebic dysentery. The latter in the form of sodium salt is known as Tryparsamide which is readily soluble in water, can be sterilised and has considerable use in the treatment of sleeping sickness.

In spite of the intensive research in arsenical derivatives, it is doubtful if any compound has been discovered which is quite without effect on the nervous system of the host, when administered over a long period. With atoxyl and its analogues, so far prepared, this action on nervous system is particularly noticeable, specially over the optic nerve.

The amino group of *para*-arsanilic acid has been condensed with various aldehydes to form the *Schiff's* bases of the type (I), with a view to reducing toxicity to the nervous system. The latter compounds readily react with sodium bisulphite to form products of the structure (II), which are readily soluble in water and are sufficiently stable to withstand sterilisation by heat or even by autoclaving.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Sodium Arsanilate with Aldehydes.—Sodium arsanilate containing about 2.5 molecules of water of crystallisation (1 part) was mixed with the aldehyde (1.25 parts) in dilute (3 : 1) alcoholic solution, so that the whole remained as a clear solution. It was then refluxed for about 2 hours on the water-bath and left overnight, when a crystalline solid separated out. The vessel was cooled in ice and the solid was filtered, washed with dilute alcohol and dried. The yield in most cases was found to be equal to the amount of sodium arsanilate taken. The products were crystallised from dilute alcohol and found to decompose without melting.

The general characteristics of the various *Schiff's* bases are recorded in Table I. Arsenic was determined by oxidation with acid permanganate according to the method of Rupp and Lehmann (*Apoth. Z.*, 1911, 26, 200), slightly modified, and nitrogen by the Dumas method.

TABLE I

Schiff's bases

Base from	Nature.	Formula.	M.W.	Arsenic		Nitrogen	
				Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.
Formal- dehyde	Colourless, hygroscopic solid	$C_5H_{11}O_5N NaAs$	298.9	25.06%	24.0%	4.7%	4.05%
Benzal- dehyde	Colourless crystals	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3N NaAs$	326.9	22.9	23.8	4.28	4.40
Anisal- dehyde	Colourless needles	$C_{14}H_{13}O_3N NaAs$	356.9	21.0	22.1	3.92	4.2
Salicylal- dehyde	Yellow shining needles	$C_{13}H_{11}O_4N NaAs$	342.9	21.84	22.7	4.08	4.4
Cinnamic aldehyde	Yellow flakes	$C_{15}H_{13}O_3N NaAs$	352.9	21.2	22.0	3.96	4.5
Dimethyl amino- benzal- dehyde	Colourless needles	$C_{15}H_{16}O_3N_2 NaAs$	369.9	20.25	21.6	7.56	7.65

Reaction with Sodium Bisulphite.—The Schiff's base, obtained above, was treated with a freshly prepared solution of a molecular quantity of sodium bisulphite, made by passing sulphur dioxide gas into an aqueous solution of a molar amount of sodium carbonate required. The mixture was gently warmed on a water-bath for a few minutes, when an almost clear solution was obtained which was allowed to stand overnight. Next day the solution was filtered, concentrated on a water-bath and then diluted with excess of alcohol, when a colourless solid separated out, which was filtered, purified by solution in water and reprecipitation with alcohol and was finally dried *in vacuo*.

The various bisulphite derivatives isolated were found to be somewhat contaminated with sodium bisulphite and/or sodium sulphite (*cf.* Ghosh and Mitra, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 10, 452). It was found difficult to remove the inorganic impurities from most of the compounds and hence the analysis of arsenic in the product indicated a lower percentage of the metal. The products in case of Schiff's bases isolated from benzal-

dehyde and anisaldehyde were, however, found pure. The former, $[\text{PhCH}(\text{SO}_3\text{Na})\text{-NH.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-As(OH)(ONa) : O}]$, gave N, 3.20 and As, 17.0%; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6\text{NSNa}_2\text{As}$ requires N, 3.24 and As, 17.38%. The corresponding product from anisaldehyde viz., $\text{CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CH}(\text{SO}_3\text{Na})\text{-NH.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-As(OH)(ONa) : O}$, gave N, 3.2 and As, 15.5%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7\text{NSNa}_2\text{As}$ requires N, 3.04 and As, 16.2 per cent.

The Schiff's base from cinnamic aldehyde and sodium arsanilate also furnished a bisulphite compound, which on analysis was found to contain 10% arsenic, whereas theory demands 13.3%. This product was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and precipitated by addition of alcohol free from aldehyde. The sulphated ash from it was found to be 43.6%, whereas $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6\text{NS}_2\text{Na}_2\text{As}$ would have afforded 37.9% solid as Na_2SO_4 by theory. Purification by reprecipitation was not effective.

This bisulphite compound was dissolved in *aqua-sterilisata* to afford 6.5% solution (p_{H} 8.6), filled into resistant ampoules and sterilised by heating at 10 lbs. pressure for 30 minutes. The p_{H} was not altered by this sterilisation. The toxicity of this sterile solution had been studied by Dr. A. N. Bose of this laboratory, by injecting it subcutaneously into mice and by comparing to that of a solution containing the same amount of arsenic as present in sodium arsanilate. It has been observed that by this substitution in the *p*-amino group of sodium arsanilate the resultant compound has been found definitely to be of lower toxicity than atoxyl. It has also been observed that the bisulphite derivative in solution does not alter in stability nor shows any increase in toxicity when stored at room temperature even for about a year. These observations indicate that the sodium bisulphite derivatives of the Schiff's bases obtained from sodium arsanilate may offer some therapeutic advantage.